

NOTA DINAS

NOMOR: B-1695/III.4.3/HK.01.00/6/2022

Yth : Kepala Biro Hukum dan Kerjasama
Dari : Kepala Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer
Hal : Permohonan Pembuatan SK
Tgl : 16 Juni 2022

Dengan hormat,

Sehubungan terdapat Agreement between The Research Center For Physics (P2F) Indonesian Institute Of Sciences (LIPI) The Republic Of Indonesia And The Center For Southeast Asian Studies (CSEAS) Kyoto University (KU) Japan pada Tahun 2021-2023 Tentang Kolaborasi Penelitian Teknologi Monitoring Dispersi Kabut Asap Dan Sirkulasi Angin Laut-Lahan Gambut Di Sumatra di Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer. Maka Perlu Menetapkan Surat Keputusan Kepala Pusat Riset Iklim Dan Atmosfer.

Adapun draft yang kami ajukan akan diserahkan kepada pihak BHKS Kawasan Bandung yaitu Ibu Rusdiati Rumiah. Berikut terlampir Draft SK dan Bahan Pendukung.(Terlampir)

Demikian atas bantuan dan perhatiannya, Kami sampaikan terima kasih.

Kepala Pusat Riset Iklim
dan Atmosfer

Albertus Sulaiman
NIP.197004281998031003

Tembusan:

- 1.Kepala Organisasi Riset Kebumian dan Maritim
2. Sekretariat Utama

KEPUTUSAN
KEPALA PUSAT RISET IKLIM DAN ATMOSFER
BADAN RISET DAN INOVASI NASIONAL NOMOR

TENTANG
TIM PELAKSANA KOLABORASI RISET
PENELITIAN TEKNOLOGI MONITORING DISPERSI KABUT ASAP DAN SIRKULASI
ANGIN LAUT-LAHAN GAMBUT DI SUMATRA
TAHUN 2022

KEPALA PUSAT RISET IKLIM DAN ATMOSFER
BADAN RISET DAN INOVASI NASIONAL

- Menimbang : a. Bahwa di Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer BRIN terdapat Agreement between The Research Center For Physics (P2F) Indonesian Institute Of Sciences (LIPI) The Republic Of Indonesia And The Center For Southeast Asian Studies (CSEAS) Kyoto University (KU) Japan pada Tahun 2021-2023 Tentang Kolaborasi Penelitian Teknologi Monitoring Dispersi Kabut Asap Dan Sirkulasi Angin Laut-Lahan Gambut Di Sumatra.
- b. Bahwa Berdasarkan Pertimbangan Sebagaimana Dimaksud Dalam Huruf A, Perlu Menetapkan Keputusan Kepala Pusat Riset Iklim Dan Atmosfer Tentang Tim Pelaksana Kolaborasi Penelitian Teknologi Monitoring Dispersi Kabut Asap Dan Sirkulasi Angin Laut-Lahan Gambut Di Sumatra Tahun 2022.
- Mengingat : 1. Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia Nomor 78 Tahun 2021 tentang Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional (Lembaran Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 2021 Nomor 192);
2. Keputusan Presiden Nomor 19/M Tahun 2021 tentang Pengangkatan Kepala Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional;
3. Peraturan Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional Nomor 1 Tahun 2021 tentang Organisasi dan Tata Kerja Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional (Berita Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 2021 Nomor 977);
4. Peraturan Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional Nomor 4 Tahun 2021 tentang Organisasi Riset (Berita Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 2021 Nomor 1082);

5. Peraturan Badan Riset Dan Inovasi Nasional Republik Indonesia Nomor 8 Tahun 2022 Tentang Tugas, Fungsi, Dan Struktur Organisasi Riset Kebumihan Dan Maritim (Berita Negara Tahun 2022 Nomor 213).

MEMUTUSKAN:

- Menetapkan : KEPUTUSAN KEPALA PUSAT RISET IKLIM DAN ATMOSFER TENTANG TIM PELAKSANA KOLABORASI PENELITIAN TEKNOLOGI MONITORING DISPERSI KABUT ASAP DAN SIRKULASI ANGIN LAUT-LAHAN GAMBUT DI SUMATRA TAHUN 2022.
- Pertama : Menetapkan Nama Yang Tercantum Dalam Kolom 2 (Dua) Lampiran Yang Merupakan Bagian Tidak Terpisahkan Dari Keputusan Ini, Sebagai Tim Pelaksana Kolaborasi Penelitian Teknologi Monitoring Dispersi Kabut Asap Dan Sirkulasi Angin Laut-Lahan Gambut Di Sumatra Tahun 2022.
- Kedua : Segala Biaya Yang Terkait Dengan Kegiatan Ini Dibebankan Pada Anggaran The Center For Southeast Asian Studies (CSEAS) Kyoto University (KU) Japan.
- Ketiga : Keputusan Ini Berlaku Sejak Tanggal Ditetapkan, Dapat Diperpanjang Maupun Dirubah Sesuai Ketentuan Yang Berlaku.

Ditetapkan di Bandung
Pada tanggal 01 Juni 2022

KEPALA PUSAT RISET IKLIM DAN
ATMOSFER

ttd.

ALBERTUS SULAIMAN

Tembusan :

1. Kepala OR Kebumihan Dan Maritim
2. Pegawai yang bersangkutan.

Salinan sesuai dengan aslinya
Plt. Kepala Biro Hukum dan Kerja Sama,

 TT ELEKTRONIK
BRIN

MILA KENCANA

LAMPIRAN
KEPUTUSAN KEPALA PUSAT RISET
IKLIM DAN ATMOSFER
NOMOR :
TANGGAL : 01 JUNI 2022

TIM PELAKSANA KOLABORASI RISET
PENELITIAN TEKNOLOGI MONITORING DISPERSI
KABUT ASAP DAN SIRKULASI ANGIN LAUT-LAHAN
GAMBUT DI SUMATRA
TAHUN 2022

Judul Riset: Penelitian Teknologi Monitoring Dispersi Kabut Asap
Dan Sirkulasi Angin Laut-Lahan Gambut Di
Sumatra.

No	Nama	NIP	Tanggung Jawab	Satuan Kerja
1.	Awaluddin, M.Si	197403142008101001	Koordinator	Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer
2.	Dr. Arief Darmawan	196904201997011002	Peneliti (dinamika atmosfer dan hujan ekstrim)	Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer
3.	Nurdiansyah	198204272014051001	Perekayasa	Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer
4.	Dr. Eng. Wendi Harjupa, ST., M. Eng	197911302001121003	Peneliti Radar	Pusat Riset Iklim dan Atmosfer
5.	Nugraheni setyaningrum, M.Si	198602062014022002	perekayasa	Pusat Riset Penginderaan Jauh
6	Doni Fernando, M.Si	198807012014021006	perekayasa	Pusat Riset Penginderaan Jauh
7	Galih Prasetya Dinanta, M.Sc	198909102014021001	perekayasa	Pusat Riset Penginderaan Jauh

KEPALA PUSAT RISET IKLIM DAN
ATMOSFER

ALBERTUS SULAIMAN

Agreement

between

**THE RESEARCH CENTER FOR PHYSICS(P2F)
INDONESIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCES (LIPI)
THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA**

and

**THE CENTER FOR SOUTHEAST ASIAN STUDIES (CSEAS)
KYOTO UNIVERSITY (KU)
JAPAN**

concerning

**RESEARCH COLLABORATION FOR MONITORING TECHNOLOGY ON
SMOKE HAZE DISPERSION AND SEA-LAND BREEZE CIRCULATION
OVER PEATLAND AREA IN SUMATERA**

This Agreement is made by and between:

1. Research Center for Physics, Indonesian Institutes of Sciences, The Republic of Indonesia, having its registered office at Building 440-442, Kawasan Puspitek, Serpong, Tangerang Selatan 15314 (hereinafter referred to as "**P2F-LIPI**") and
2. Center for Southeast Asian Studies, The Kyoto University of Japan, having its registered office at 46 Shimoadachi-cho, Yoshida Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8501 (hereinafter referred to as "**CSEAS-KU**").

hereinafter referred to collectively as the "**Parties**" and each individually as a "**Party**";

Desiring to establish relations between the Parties in the approved research and development field on the principle of mutual benefits concerning scientific research cooperation and as an implementation arrangement of the scientific research activity entitled "**Research Collaboration For Monitoring Technology on Smoke Haze Dispersion and Sea-Land Breeze Circulation Over Peatland Area in Sumatera**";

Referring to the Memorandum of Understanding between LIPI and KU on Scientific and Research Cooperation signed at Kyoto on 10 December 2019 and at Jakarta on December 2019;

Pursuant to the prevailing laws and regulation in their respective countries as well as their respective government's procedure and policies on international technical cooperation;

HAVE AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

ARTICLE 1 OBJECTIVES

The objective of this Agreement is to establish a framework for cooperation between the Parties to conduct Joint Regional Development Research on Peatland Monitoring in Sumatra particularly on smoke haze dispersion and sea-land breeze circulation.

ARTICLE 2 SCOPE OF ACTIVITIES

- a) Joint research and investigation on atmospheric dynamic over peatland;
- b) Joint development of the methodology and algorithms of Radar monitoring for smoke from peatfire;
- c) Exchange of scientific materials and equipment, publications, and informations;
- d) Exchange of researchers and staff;
- e) Exchange and utilizing of data and information in the areas of atmospheric sciences;
- f) Joint Publication;
- g) Capacity building development for researchers, staff and students of the Parties
- h) Joint symposiums, workshops, and scientific meetings.

ARTICLE 3 IMPLEMENTATION

1. Depending on the nature and degree of the collaboration, the terms of cooperation for each specify activity implemented under this Agreement, including but not limited to the details of the activities such scope of activities and program or project schedule, personnel involved, financial aspects, responsibilities undertaken by the Parties and other necessary matters that are not covered by this Agreement, shall be mutually discussed and agreed

upon in writing by the Parties on the Plan of Operation(s) individually and separately prior to the initiation of that activity.

2. All activities will be carried out in Indonesia and Japan
3. In carrying out the terms of this Agreement, the following persons are designated as contact representatives as follow:
 - a. P2F-LIPI : Dr. Albertus Sulaiman
Address : P2F-LIPI, Kawasan Puspiptek, Serpong, Tangerang Selatan
15314, Indonesia
Phone : 081317151925
E-mail : albertus.sulaiman@lipi.go.id
 - b. CSEAS-KU : Dr. Osamu Kozan
Address : 46 Shimoadachi-cho, Yoshida, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8501,
Japan
Phone : +81-75-753-9652
E-mail : kozan@cseas.kyoto-u.ac.jp
4. The contact representatives of the Parties agree to communicate in good time to discuss and shall maintain regular contact and regular report to their director.
5. All notices to be given under this Agreement should be in official written form and shall be deemed delivered when delivered in person or received by email, certified mail, return receipt requested, addressed to the recipients designated above, subject to any change of address, written notice of which will promptly be provided.
6. All letters, reports and other documents for the implementation of the Project and the bilateral discussion between the Parties shall be in English. If the indications are in both English and Indonesian languages, and there is discrepancy between the English version and the Indonesian version of the sentences, the English-language version shall prevail.
7. Relevant changes regarding the Parties' contact representatives will not require an amendment of this Agreement. The Parties will keep each other informed about the details of their contact representatives.

ARTICLE 4 CONTRIBUTION BY P2F-LIPI

Subject to the applicable laws and regulation in Indonesia, the available resources and with agreement of the Parties, P2F-LIPI will:

1. Assist in arranging research permit and other necessary paperwork (such as export permits) from the Indonesian government to facilitate joint research visits and joint fieldwork involving researchers and expert from CSEAS-KU in Indonesia.
2. Assign qualified experts and researchers to work on collaborative project involving the activities under this Agreement.
3. Develop methodology and algoritme regarding atmospheric observation over peatland area.

ARTICLE 5 CONTRIBUTION BY CSEAS-KU

Subject to the applicable laws and regulation in Japan, the available resources and with agreement of the Parties, CSEAS-KU will:

1. Assign qualified experts and researchers to work on collaborative project involving the activities under this Agreement.
2. Provide the technology transfer of atmospheric radar in the context of capacity building for LIPI staff through training in Indonesia or in Japan.
3. Provide necessary equipment and basic facilities for the execution of its own duties on the collaborative project under this Agreement and responsible for the delivery such equipment.
4. Assist in arranging research permit and other necessary paperwork (such as work permit and export permits) from Japan government to facilitate joint research visits and joint fieldwork involving researchers and expert from P2F-LIPI in Japan.
5. Based on the prior written consent of the Parties, provide in funding for P2F-LIPI research staff in visiting CSEAS of KU (transportation, accommodation, insurance and daily allowance).

ARTICLE 6 FINANCIAL ARRANGEMENT

All financial arrangements for the implementation of this Agreement will be specified in the Plan of Operation(s) and is subject to the availability of funds of the Parties and their applicable laws and regulation.

ARTICLE 7 LIMITATION OF PERSONNEL ACTIVITIES

1. The Parties shall ensure that their personnel(s) engaged in activities under this Agreement will observe, respect, and comply with the laws and regulations, and policies of the host country.
2. The Parties agree to be responsible for the negligent acts or omissions of their own researchers, staff and its associates while acting within the scope of their employment during the term of this Agreement.
3. The Violation of this article may result in revocation of permit of stay of the personnel concerned by the competent authorities as well as other necessary measures in accordance with the prevailing laws and regulations of the host country.

ARTICLE 8 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

1. Any Intellectual Property (IP) including know-how, methods, and technical information brought by one of the Parties for the implementation of activities under this Agreement shall remain the property of that Party. However, that Party is liable for ensuring that the

IP is not the result of the infringement of any third Party's legitimate Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Further that Party shall be liable for any claim made by a third Party on the ownership and legality of the use of the IP which is brought in by the aforementioned Party for the implementation of the cooperation activities under this Agreement.

2. Sole Application for Patents:

When any person belonging to either Party intends to file a patent application on an invention made independently by said person during the implementation of the Joint Research, such application shall be done by the Party to which said person belongs; provided, however, that such Party has given prior notice thereof to the other Party.

3. Share of Intellectual Property Rights:

Any IP generated from the Joint Research shall be jointly owned by the Parties, unless otherwise agreed upon. The terms and condition for commercialization of intellectual property jointly developed or created by the Parties shall be determined on a case by case basis by the Parties. Should the IP resulted from the activities under this Agreement be used for commercial purposes by one Party, the other Party shall be entitled to the royalties obtained from the exploitation of such property on the basis of the principle of equitable contribution. In such case, the object of the research activities conducted under this Agreement shall constitute a part of contribution of the Parties from which the object derives. The value of the object as part of contribution will be measured by taking into account the following factors:

- a) the scarcity of the object (the rarer the object is, the higher its value will be);
- b) the commercial value of the result of the research (the higher its commercial value is the higher its worth).

4. Joint Application for Patents:

- a) When a person belonging to either Party intends to file a patent application on an invention based on the results obtained from the Joint Research (hereinafter referred to as the "Research Results"), the patent application shall be made jointly by all Parties; however, this shall not apply to cases in which the other Party's consent not to file a joint application has been obtained.
- b) In cases of filing a joint application as set forth in the preceding paragraph, the Parties shall enter into a separate joint application agreement after mutual consultation on their respective shares of the patent rights.

5. Patent Fees:

The Parties shall bear the costs and expenses incurred during the patent application process and any other cost relating to the prosecution and maintenance of the patent, which shall be determined based on their respective shares.

6. The utilization of the IP of any research activities under this Agreement outside the territories of the Republic of Indonesia and the Japan by one of the Parties requires prior written approval from the other Party on a case by case basis.

7. Each Party shall not, without the prior written consent of the other Owner Party, which consent shall not be unreasonably withheld, assign or otherwise transfer to any third party all or any part of its right, title and interest in and to the jointly owned IP, except that

each Party may, upon prior written notice to the other Party, make such assignment and transfer to any of its project members or any third party not-for-profit organization, provided, however, that such assignment or transfer shall not limit the rights of the Party hereunder in respect of such IP.

ARTICLE 9 CONFIDENTIALITY

1. Each Party shall treat Information ("Information") which is (i) disclosed by the other Party in writing (or in an electronic medium) with a representation that it is confidential information; and (ii) disclosed by the other Party orally with a notice to the effect that it is confidential (limited to those where the content is confirmed in writing or by electronic medium within fifteen (15) days after the disclosure), the Information that falls under (i) or (ii) as Confidential Information ("Confidential Information") and the disclosing Party and receiving Party of Confidential Information, respectively, "Disclosing Party" and "Receiving Party" and restrict access thereto to those of its employees, students or agents who need to know it for the purpose of performing the Project under this Agreement and who shall have been made aware that such Confidential Information is to be treated as confidential and shall not disclose or leak any of it to any third party.
2. In order to preserve confidentiality whilst discussing the Project with Parties who are not signatories to this Agreement, each Party shall not disclose information disclosed to it by the other Parties to any third party without the prior written consent of the disclosing Party.
3. Each Party shall not use any Confidential Information for any purpose other than the purpose of this Agreement.
4. The restrictions as to the use and disclosure set out above shall not apply to:
 - a) any of the Information which is or becomes public other than by unauthorised publication in breach of this Agreement; or
 - b) any of the Information which is shown by written or other tangible evidence to have been known to the Receiving Party prior to the date of the disclosure; or
 - c) any of the Information which is lawfully acquired by the Receiving Party from an independent source having a right to disclose the same; or
 - d) any Information which is independently developed by an employee of the Receiving Party who has not had access to any of the Information disclosed to the Receiving Party by the Disclosing Party; or
 - e) any situation that the Receiving Party is required to be disclosed by law or regulations or requirements by any public institution shall be exempt from the confidentiality obligation under preceding Article, but only to the extent required by such obligation of disclosure. In which case the Receiving Party shall endeavor to ensure that the Disclosing Party may has a reasonable chance to take measures to protect the secrecy of such Confidential Information.
5. After the termination of the Agreement (or during the term of the Agreement if deemed reasonably necessary), upon request by the Disclosing Party, the Receiving Party shall

either return or destroy all documentary and electronic or other tangible (including all copies thereof) embodiments of the Disclosing Party's Confidential Information without delay in accordance with the instructions of the Disclosing Party.

ARTICLE 10
PUBLICATION AND DISCLOSURE OF DATA AND TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

1. All materials including data or information that are collected during the implementation of the Agreement from the Indonesia territory are the property of the Government of Republic of Indonesia represented by P2F-LIPI. Therefore, CSEAS-KU recognizes the prior right of P2F-LIPI to ultimate possession of all Indonesian materials obtained in the course of field works in the Indonesian boundaries within the project.
2. The Parties shall share observational data and any technical knowledge (excluding IP) obtained from the Joint Research under this Agreement. Prior consultation, proper descriptions of the data sources, and co-authorship are required for any operational data use and for any publications using the data at all time. Each Party shall disclose the contents of any publications based on this Joint Research under this Agreement and gain the written consent of the other Party before the document is published. Neither Party shall either disclose or divulge any technical knowledge obtained from the other Party to any third party without the approval of the other Party. For a better understanding of the characteristics of Peatland in Sumatra, observational data (excluding IP) obtained in Indonesia from cooperative research among CSEAS-KU and P2F- LIPI shall also be considered to be shared after mutual consultation.
3. The Parties will ensure that any publication about the relationship between the Parties is accurate. Only the approved name and logo of the other Party may be used in any such materials.
4. The Indonesian side of the Parties shall contribute at least in the writing of any section related to materials obtained in Indonesia to ensure that the co-authorship comply with international code of co-authorship.
5. Parts of the publications shall be published in International Journal with the data and samples gathered under this Agreement.

ARTICLE 11
EQUIPMENT

Ownership of any equipment or facilities bought or fabricated by a Party will be property of such Party.

ARTICLE 12
SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTES

Any dispute, controversy, and difference as to the interpretation of this Agreement shall be settled by mutual consultation between the Parties based on the principles of cooperation,

equality and sincerity, without reference to any third parties or international tribunals. If agreement cannot be achieved, settlement will be subject to the exclusive jurisdiction of a court of competent jurisdiction: (a) in Osaka-shi, Osaka, Japan if CSEAS-KU is the defendant; and (b) in Kota Jakarta Pusat, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia if P2F-LIPI is the defendant. The Parties hereby agree to submit to the exclusive jurisdiction of the relevant court and hereby waive any claim or defense that such court lacks jurisdiction over the Dispute or any Party or constitutes an inconvenient or improper forum or venue. In addition, the Parties hereby waive any right to a trial by jury in any procedures

ARTICLE 13 FORCE MAJEURE

1. In the event that either Party is delayed or impeded in the performance of its obligations hereunder this Agreement by reason of acts of God, floods, storms, earthquake (natural disaster), strikes, lockouts, riots, sabotage, battles, wars, embargo, civil commotion, labor dispute, fire explosions, failure of utilities, mechanical breakdowns, material shortages, disease, failure of any governmental approval required for full performance or other causes beyond its control of the Parties ("force majeure") shall not be deemed to be a breach of this Agreement, provided that the Party so prevented from complying herewith shall not have procured such force majeure, shall have used reasonable diligence to avoid such force majeure or ameliorate its effects, and shall continue to take all actions within its power to comply as fully as possible with the terms of the Agreement.
2. In the event of such Force Majeure occurred, each Party promptly inform the other Party of the nature of the relevant cause and of the expected duration of the relevant delay or impediment no later than 30 (thirty) calendar days from the occurrence of a state of compulsion supported by a statement from the competent authority.
3. After the Parties agree on the occurrence of Force Majeure, the implementation of the cooperation will then be re-determined by the Parties.

ARTICLE 14 LAWS AND REGULATIONS

This Agreement shall be governed and construed under the laws of the Republic of Indonesia and of Japan, as appropriate, depending upon the location of the particular activity undertaken as part of this Agreement. All activities undertaken pursuant to this Agreement shall be subject to the applicable rules and regulations of the Parties, as well as the availability of appropriated funds, personnel, and other resources of each Party.

ARTICLE 15 AMENDMENT

Each Party may request in writing an amendment or modification of any part of this Agreement. Any amendment or modification shall be agreed upon by all Parties in writing and shall constitute part of this Agreement. Such amendment or modification shall form an integral part of this Agreement and shall enter into force on such a date as may be determined by all Parties.

ARTICLE 16
ENTRY INTO FORCE, DURATION AND TERMINATION

1. This Agreement shall be in effect on the date of signature of the last Party and shall remain in effect for a period of 3 (three) years and may be extended with the mutual consent of the Parties in writing.
2. This Agreement may be terminated by either Party after giving at least 6 (six) months written notice to the other Party prior to the intended date of termination.
3. The termination of this Agreement shall not affect the validity of the contract or activities made during the period of validity of this Agreement until the completion of such contracts or activities, unless otherwise decided by the Parties.
4. Article 8, 10 and 17 shall survive upon the termination of this Agreement.

ARTICLE 17
OTHER PROVISIONS

1. Any rights or obligations under this Agreement shall not be assigned, transferred to or succeeded by a third party without the other Party's consent.
2. If governmental license or any other authorizations for the activities under this Agreement including, but not limited to, the access to materials are required under the applicable laws and regulations of the jurisdiction of a Party (the "Responsible Party"), Responsible Party shall be responsible for obtaining or maintaining such authorizations. In addition, if any procedure is legally required to be taken by the other Party for such authorizations, the Responsible Party shall notify the other Party in writing of the existence and content of such procedure and fully cooperate with such Party in completing such procedure.
3. In no event shall a Party be liable to the other Party for any special, consequential, incidental, punitive or other indirect damages (including, but not limited to, damages for loss of profit or business interruption) that may be suffered or incurred by the other Party arising out of or in connection with the performance of, or the failure or inability to perform, this Agreement, even in the event of fault, tort (including negligence), strict liability, breach of contract or breach of warranty, and even if such damages are foreseeable under the circumstances or it has been advised of the possibility thereof, provided, however, that the limitation of liability of a Party set forth above in this Section shall not apply to or otherwise restrict liability for death of or injury (including sickness or disease) to any natural person caused by or resulting from the negligence or willful misconduct of such Party.
4. P2F-LIPI hereby acknowledges and agrees that CSEAS-KU now contracts, or may in the future contract, with a third party (the "Administrative Agent") for the management and administrative handling of its selected intellectual properties which it owns or controls now or in the future, including those that may accrue under this Agreement, and that such Administrative Agent may contact or communicate with P2F-LIPI for administrative issues concerning such intellectual properties. For the avoidance of doubt, and notwithstanding any other provision of this Agreement, CSEAS-KU may disclose to its Administrative Agent the Confidential Information of P2F-LIPI and any results for the said purpose; provided, however, that the Administrative Agent shall consent, in advance of such disclosure, to assume all the same obligations of confidentiality and

limited use as have been assumed by CSEAS-KU hereunder in respect of such Confidential Information or results, as the case may be.

5. Each Party hereby acknowledges that, in the event of any actual or threatened breach by it of this Agreement, including, but not limited to, the actual or threatened unauthorized use or disclosure by it of any information which it shall have an obligation hereunder to maintain in confidence, the other Party so breached will suffer an irreparable injury, which might entitle it to seek equitable relief, including, but not limited to, a preliminary injunction or other provisional judicial relief.
6. Notwithstanding any other provision of this Agreement, and if applicable, P2F-LIPI does not hereby intend, and shall not be obligated or required, to disclose, provide, furnish or otherwise transfer to CSEAS-KU or any of its Project members and other employees any re-export-controlled information or item which shall be subject to a license or other authorization for re-export required under export control laws and regulations of the United States of America such as, for example, U.S. Export Administration Regulations or under any equivalents thereof in the jurisdiction of P2F-LIPI. If the P2F-LIPI makes such disclosure, provision, furnishing or transfer, the P2F-LIPI shall notify CSEAS-KU in advance in writing thereof and obtain from CSEAS-KU the prior written consent thereto, which consent may be withheld at its sole and final discretion.
7. Nothing contained in this Agreement is intended, or shall be deemed, to give, grant or otherwise convey to a Party any rights, titles, licenses, permissions or approvals for any military activities or any other military purposes, and the other Party shall not be obligated hereby to do so in the future.
8. The Parties shall exercise their respective rights and perform their respective obligations under this Agreement in compliance with all applicable present and future laws and regulations.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the undersigned, have signed this Agreement.

DONE in duplicate in English Language. Each copy which has been provided to the Parties is considered as being equally authentic. Any translations are for convenience only and will have no force or effect on the interpretation hereof.

**Research Center for Physics,
Indonesian Institute of Sciences**

**Dr. Rike Yudianti
Director**

Date: 14 / Sept 2021

**Center for Southeast Asian Studies,
Kyoto University**

**Prof. Dr. Yoko Hayami
Director**

Date: 31st August 2021